

IMPROVED MAGNETIZATION OF 3Y-ZrO₂/ Ba-HEXAFERRITE COMPOSITE BY POST-PLASTIC DEFORMATION

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SUMMARY: Microstructure, deformation behavior and magnetic properties of 3 mol%-Y₂O₃-partially-stabilized zirconia (3Y-ZrO₂) containing 20 wt% barium hexaferrite (BaFe₁₂O₁₉) were studied. Post-plastic deformation for the composite at high temperatures (i.e. hot-forging) led to the formation of textile microstructure of the platelet BaFe₁₂O₁₉ grains. Saturation magnetization and coercivity were improved by the post-plastic deformation process, presumably due to the alignment of easy-magnetization axis of BaFe₁₂O₁₉ grains.

KEYWORDS: tetragonal zirconia polycrystals, barium hexaferrite, magnetoplumbite, plasticity, textile microstructure, hot-forging, magnetization, coercive force

INTRODUCTION

Tetragonal zirconia polycrystal (TZP) ceramics, typically 3 mol%-Y₂O₃-partially-stabilized zirconia (3Y-ZrO₂), have attracted much attention because of their excellent mechanical properties and ionic conductivity [1-3]. TZP ceramics including magnetoplumbite-type (M-type) ferrite particles have been recently studied to give some magnetic properties for zirconia [4-6]. Ceramic particles with magnetoplumbite or related β -Al₂O₃ crystal structure generally possess hexagonal platelike or needlelike shapes. It has been reported that incorporating such second-phase particles into Y₂O₃- or CeO₂-doped zirconia improves their fracture toughness due to the crack deflection around the anisotropic second phase, e.g., 8 wt%-Y₂O₃-doped-ZrO₂/20 vol% Na- β -Al₂O₃ [7] and Ce-TZP/La(Fe,Al)₁₂O₁₉ [6] composites, or due to the modifying transformability of tetragonal zirconia phase, for example, MnO-doped Ce-TZP/Al₂O₃ (i.e. Ce-TZP/Al₂O₃/CeMnAl₁₁O₁₉) composite [8].

Barium hexaferrite, BaFe₁₂O₁₉, is a typical M-type compound, with platelike shape and has the easy-magnetization axis perpendicular to the basal plane. It is widely used as economical permanent magnets. Anisotropic magnets with excellent magnetic properties can be prepared

by the application of a magnetic field during pressing and sintering (i.e. magnetic-field-assisting alignment) [9]. This results in the rotation of the particles so that easy directions tend to become aligned parallel to the magnetic field [9]. When $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ is used as a dispersoid material in TZP, magnetic-field-assisting alignment will be effective to improve some magnetic properties, similarly to the above-mentioned single-phase $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$. However, in this case linear $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ agglomerates along with the magnetic field may be produced in the TZP matrix, presumably resulting in large fracture origin.

Because $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ particles have platelike shapes, textile microstructure can be formed by hot-pressing and hot-forging (post-plastic deformation) even if they are embedded in TZP matrix, similarly to the elongated grains within polycrystalline Al_2O_3 [10,11], Si_3N_4 [12], SiAlON [13] and SiC [14].

In this work, a 3 mol%-yttria-doped TZP/barium hexaferrite (3Y-TZP/ $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$) composite was fabricated by conventional hot-pressing method. Some magnetic and mechanical properties were evaluated for both as-hot-pressed and post-deformed specimens to show the alignment effects of anisotropic hexaferrite particles. This paper also shows the usefulness of hot-working techniques not only for the structural ceramics but also for the functional ones.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Sample preparation

Commercially available 3Y-TZP (TZ-3Y, 0.3 μm , Tosoh Co., Ltd., Japan) and $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (2-3 μm , Kojundo Chemical Laboratory Co., Ltd., Japan) powders were used as the starting materials. The $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ content in this investigation was chosen as 20 wt% (22 vol%) because this composition is almost the same as the second-phase-percolation limitation. It can be partly comparable to the reported works on TZP/20 wt% hexaferrite systems by Kojima et al. [4-6], although their chemical compositions are rather different from the present work. The 3Y-TZP and $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ powders were wet-ball-milled in ethanol for 100 h using zirconia balls in a polyethylene pot. The mixed slurry was dried, subsequently dry-ball-milled for 24 h, and then, sieved through a 150-mesh screen. The mixed powder was hot-pressed at 1250°C for 1 h under a pressure of 30 MPa in an argon atmosphere. The hot-pressed disk was 44 mm in diameter and 5.0 mm in thickness. The relative density of the composite was 99.0 %, which was measured by Archimedes method in toluene. Experimental procedures are schematically summarized in Fig. 1.

Evaluation

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was used to determine the crystalline phases. The microstructure was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The hot-pressed disk was cut into rectangular specimens with the size of 2.8 x 2.8 x 3.6 mm for compressive test, which was carried out at 1200, 1250 and 1300°C in air with the compressive axis parallel to the hot-pressing direction. After the compressive test (about 80% in true strain), the size of the deformed specimen became ~ 4.2 x 4.2 x 1.6 mm. Appearances of the 3Y-TZP/20 wt% $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ composite before and after compressive deformation are indicated in Fig. 2.

Magnetic properties were measured for the as-hot-pressed and plastically-deformed ($\epsilon_t = \sim 0.8$) specimens using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) with a maximum applied field of 1.27 MA/m (16 kOe). To minimize the difference in shape magnetic anisotropy of two samples, as-hot-pressed composite was also machined into the size of about 4.2 x 4.2 x 1.6 mm. Specimen settings in the magnetic field are indicated in Fig. 3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Constituent Phases of 3Y-TZP/BaFe₁₂O₁₉ Composite

The XRD analysis revealed that the composite mainly consisted of tetragonal ZrO₂ and BaFe₁₂O₁₉. Some monoclinic ZrO₂ was also detected, which was formed presumably due to the internal thermal stress induced by the anisotropic thermal expansion of BaFe₁₂O₁₉ particles. Y₂O₃-doped zirconia and BaFe₁₂O₁₉ seem to be phase-compatible under the present experimental conditions. This is probably because (1) ZrO₂ and Fe₂O₃ are principally phase compatible (with a little solid-solubility) [15], (2) Ba²⁺ ion is stable in the magnetoplumbite structure [16], and (3) Zr⁴⁺ and Y³⁺ ions are hardly incorporated in this structure [16].

Fig. 1: Schematic illustration of experimental procedure.

Fig. 2: Appearance of the 3Y-TZP/20 wt% BaFe₁₂O₁₉ composite before and after compressive deformation.

Fig. 3: Specimen directions in the magnetic field.

Fig.4 : Strain rate vs. flow stress at various temperatures for the 3Y-TZP/20 wt% BaFe₁₂O₁₉ composite.

Fig.5 : SEM photographs of the post-deformed 3Y-TZP/20 wt% BaFe₁₂O₁₉ composite: Deformation was performed at 1200°C, $\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 4.7 \times 10^{-4}/s$.

Compressive Deformation Behavior

After the compressive test up to about 80% of true strain ($\sim 55\%$ of nominal strain), slight barreling was observed for all specimens, but no obvious surface-crack was observed (Fig. 2). Sufficient plastic deformation could be achieved at relatively low temperatures and low flow stresses. The values of true flow stress at the true strain of 0.5 were plotted as a function of the strain rate in Fig. 4. A linear relationship between the true flow stress and the true strain rate was obtained in the log-scale. Strain rate sensitivity values, which were obtained from the slope lines, were $m \sim 0.2$ (i.e., stress exponent, $n \sim 5$), indicating that the deformation mechanism may be governed by the dislocation motion. The deformation mode can be explained by the size of dispersoid, BaFe₁₂O₁₉ agglomerates of about 5 - 10 μm , which may be too large to deform mainly by grain boundary sliding. The decomposition temperature of the BaFe₁₂O₁₉ in air atmosphere is in the vicinity of 1450°C, although it strongly depends on the oxygen partial pressure [17]. The compression-testing temperatures, 1200-1300°C in this study, must be sufficiently high for the dislocation motion inside the hexaferrite particles. Fine-grained TZP matrix must accommodate the deformation strain by the grain boundary sliding. Figure 5 shows SEM photographs of the post-deformed 3Y-TZP/20 wt% BaFe₁₂O₁₉ composite. BaFe₁₂O₁₉ particles tended to align so that their c axes became parallel to the compressive axis.

Magnetic Properties Before and After Deformation

Figure 6 shows magnetization hysteresis loops of the 3Y-ZrO₂/20 wt% BaFe₁₂O₁₉ composite. As-hot-pressed and post-deformed (deformation temperature: 1250°C, initial strain rate: $1.2 \times 10^{-4}/s$, true strain: 80%) specimens were evaluated under two different magnetic-field directions as shown in Fig.3. Both for the perpendicular (\perp) and parallel ($//$) directions, post-deformed specimens showed larger hysteresis loop than as hot-pressed specimens; for both directions, saturation magnetization and coercivity of the former were ~ 1.7 and ~ 2.7 times larger than those of the latter, respectively. The value of the saturation magnetization of the

post-deformed specimen in parallel direction was 98.8 mT, which can be corrected as 494 mT of single-phase $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ considered from the concentration of hexaferrite particles.

The shape-magnetic anisotropy macroscopically causes the specimens in perpendicular direction to be more easily magnetized. On the other hand, when the hexaferrite platelets align inside the composite due to the mechanical pressing, the magneto-crystalline anisotropy microscopically causes the specimens in parallel direction to be more easily magnetized. In this study, the saturation magnetization of the parallel direction was larger than that of the perpendicular direction for both of the as hot-pressed and the post deformed specimens, despite of the disadvantage from the shape-magnetic anisotropy. This result suggests that the hexagonal platelets are aligned to form textile microstructure, and thus, the improvement in magnetic properties is mainly attributable to the alignment of the hexaferrite platelet particles. In addition, mechanical poling and sub-grain-boundary formation via the large-scale deformation presumably contributed to the improvement.

Fig. 6: Room-temperature magnetic properties of the 3Y-TZP/20 wt% $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ composite measured under the magnetic field up to 1.27 MA/m (16.0 kOe).

The post plastic deformation improved magnetic properties of the magnetic-particle-dispersed composite, similarly to the conventional slurry pressing in the magnetic field used for anisotropic permanent magnets prepared by monolithic hexaferrites. For the composite, since the post deformation does not form large linear agglomerates, which may be formed by the conventional slurry pressing in the magnetic fields, it will be a promising solution to obtain good magnetic properties of a magnetic composite without severe loss of mechanical properties. The dispersion state of the hexaferrite particles must be improved for this purpose, and in situ composite techniques [4-6], where hexaferrite particles are formed during sintering process, may solve the problem. The absolute values of the coercive force in Fig.7 were rather small as barium hexaferrite, due to the relatively large size of the hexaferrite particles, but the coercivity must be also improved by preparing in situ nanocomposites. The post-deformation technique in the magnetic-particle-dispersed composites is applicable to another functionality of the other ceramic/ceramic composite systems; for example anisotropically controlling the ionic conductivity of the β -alumina dispersed ZrO_2 .

The composite developed in this study could have a remote stress-sensing function, on the analogy of the ceramic/ferromagnetic metal composites [18-20], and such a function enables to largely improve the reliability of ceramic materials.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work focused on developing textile microstructure and improving magnetic properties of the 3Y-ZrO₂/Ba-hexaferrite composite by post-plastic deformation. In summary, A 3Y-ZrO₂/Ba-hexaferrite composite has been fabricated by powder metallurgical processes. Due to the spontaneous magnetization of the BaFe₁₂O₁₉ powder used, agglomerated particles (5 to 10 μ m) were observed in the composite. However, they homogeneously dispersed in the TZP matrix from a macroscopic viewpoint.

The deformation mechanism of the composite at 1200-1300°C was very likely associated with the dislocation motion of the relatively large hexaferrite particles. The composite had sufficient deformability at low flow stress.

Post-plastic deformation on the composite improved both saturation magnetization and coercivity, probably due to the alignment of the hexaferrite platelet particles. In order to obtain good magnetic properties for magnetic-particles-dispersed composites, the post-plastic deformation can be a new complementary technique to the conventional slurry pressing under the magnetic field.

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